

Multi-UAV Planning in Search and Rescue Missions using Optimal Search Effort Allocation

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Abstract—In this paper we present a new search planning method for a coordinated swarm of UAVs based on the Theory of Search which provides a precise and robust probabilistic model for Search and Rescue (SAR) operations where lost victims need to be found as soon as possible. Using any “a priori” information about the victims’ positions, a probability density function for each one is built and used to compute the optimal search effort allocation for the resources available. The priority assigned to each region of the area of interest is derived for such allocation using probability theory. This defines a set of priority sub-areas that span all the possible locations where a victim could be located. The optimal UAV distribution and order at which each sub-area is visited is computed using a Traveling Salesman Problem solver. The coverage paths within each sub-area are computed using an energy-aware path planner. We also address how to solve potential collisions with the terrain and/or other UAVs of the team. We have performed extensive simulations to validate our approach obtaining promising results in terms of probability of finding the victims and path feasibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the development in Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) in the last decades, they have become an ideal tool for Search and Rescue (SAR) missions not only due elimination of human safety risks in hazardous environments but also because of their versatility and easy deployment. Several works [1], [2], [3] have already tap into the research of using UAS for SAR missions in a systematic manner.

Search and rescue mathematical foundations can be found in the Theory of Search [4], [5], [6], [7], a branch of Operations Research dedicated to the study of optimal search in different scenarios. Several authors extended and refined the theory to more general scenarios [8], [9] after the original publications. Many reviews and books have been published with extended revision on the state of the Theory of Search [10], [11], [12]. This theory has been successfully adapted and applied in real SAR missions. It was used to recover the H-Bombs lost in the southern coast of Spain in 1966 after a B-52 military aircraft and a tanker crashed [13]. It was also applied to develop the SAROPS [14] (Search and Rescue Optimal Planning System) software that the U.S. Coast Guard uses for SAR missions. This software was used

to find the Air France Flight 447, an Airbus 330-200 with 228 passengers and crew, that disappeared over the South Atlantic during a night flight from Rio de Janeiro Brazil to Paris France on 1 June 2009 [15].

A recent paper [16] follows a similar approach to solve a similar problem to those presented in this paper. It makes use of the well-known Travel Salesman Problem and coverage path planning to compute the optimal path to find a certain amount of lost targets after an earthquake. However, it lacks a solid probabilistic foundation to systematically assign priority levels to each target and often uses arbitrary metrics.

Another paper [17] presents a route planning algorithm for maritime search and rescue missions with moving targets. It provides a sophisticated and precise probabilistic model that addresses many characteristics of these kind of dynamic missions. It also develops the corresponding multi-UAV path planning. However, the application is limited to maritime scenarios and lacks any consideration about the physical maneuvering and autonomy of the devices used.

In this paper, we present a new search and rescue planning method for a coordinated swarm of drones based on the Theory of Search to provide a precise and robust probabilistic model. The information obtained through it is then adapted to compute realistic (i.e. plausible for real UAVs and in real-life conditions) and energy-efficient plans for real use case scenarios taking into account the physical characteristics and limitations of the drones used and the terrain elevation. We also provide a set of rules to solve many conflicts that may arise during the mission execution.

This work is organized as follows: in Section II we present the theoretical framework and computations needed to find the optimal search effort allocation for a multi-seeker multi-target scenario in search and rescue missions. In Subsection III-A and Subsection III-B, we define an algorithm to obtain the paths for a swarm of drones using the previously computed optimal search effort allocation using Traveling Salesman Problem-based models and energy-aware coverage path planning. In Subsection III-C, we address the issues that may arise in the previous section due to autonomy and physical constraints and potential risk of collision with other drones and the terrain. In Subsection III-D we discuss how to transform the obtained paths into actual trajectories. In Section IV, we discuss the deployment of this approach into real SAR missions and field tests. In Section V, we analyze the simulation results to test the mathematical correctness of the base theory and to show the feasibility of the methodology in real missions using simulated real UAV

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models. Section VI closes the paper with the conclusions.

II. OPTIMAL SEARCH EFFORT ALLOCATION

Let us consider n_T targets $T = \{t_i\}_{i=1}^{n_T}$ that we need to find and that are known to be within a rectangular region $A \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. All the information available “a priori” is a probability density function $p_t : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ for the position, considered static, of each target t .

A team of n_S seekers is at our disposal. However, the total search effort, i.e., the effective area that can be searched, is limited to a total of Φ_T area units. If we want to make our search optimal, we would need to correctly distribute the search effort throughout the area to maximize our chances of finding at least a target. For that, we define the search effort density $\sigma : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ which can be interpreted as the ratio between the effective area scanned and the actual physical surface area covered.

Consider also a discretization $\mathcal{D}(A)$ of the area A that divides the region into $n_x \cdot n_y$ rectangular cells (see Figure 1) of area ΔA ($\sum_{c \in \mathcal{D}(A)} \Delta A = \text{surface of } A$).

Fig. 1: Discretization \mathcal{D} into $n_x \cdot n_y$ rectangular cells $c \in \mathcal{D}(A)$ of the rectangular region A

For each cell $c \in \mathcal{D}(A)$, we can compute the probability of a single $t \in T$ target being within it $P_t(c) = \iint_c p_t(\mathbf{x}) dA$ ($\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$ is the position vector). Then also, probability for k targets is

$$P^{(k)}(c) = \sum_{\substack{\forall T_n \subset T \\ |T_n|=n}} \prod_{t \in T_n} P_t(c) \prod_{t' \in T/T_n} [1 - P_{t'}(c)]. \quad (1)$$

This expression fulfills $\sum_{k=0}^{n_T} P^{(k)}(c) = 1$.

At the same time, let us consider that each seeker is equipped with a detector (e.g. a regular or thermal camera, phone signal detectors or similar equipment although this theory is detector-agnostic) that takes infinitesimal glimpses at the local environment in search of a target. By definition, these scanners are not perfect and the detection probability is not unity. Each seeker-detector combination has a certain single-target detection rate per time unit defined as

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{A_{\text{covered}}} \frac{dA_{\text{scanned}}}{dt} \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

where A_{covered} is the physical area covered while A_{scanned} is the effective area scanned.

With this, the probability of not finding any target after a local scan between $\tau = t_0$ and $\tau = t$ if k of them are present within the scanned region is:

$$P_{\text{ND}}^{(k)} = \prod_{\tau \in (t_0, t)} [1 - k\gamma d\tau] = e^{-k \int_{t_0}^t \gamma d\tau}, \quad (3)$$

which is a Volterra integral (by definition $\prod_{x \in (a, b)} [1 + f(x)dx] = \exp \int_a^b f(x)dx$), the equivalent of the Riemann integral but with multiplication in place of summation. We can mathematically define the search effort density as

$$\sigma = \int_{t_0}^t \gamma d\tau \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

which by virtue of Equation 2 is the quantitative expression of the previously given qualitative definition. Using Equation 3 and Equation 4 we can define the probability of not detecting any target if the seeker and k targets coincide in c as

$$P_{\text{ND}|c}^{(k)}(\sigma) = e^{-k\sigma(c)}. \quad (5)$$

For $k = 1$, this is equivalent to the exponential detection law defined in the original 1950s papers [5] and [6].

Using Equation 1 and Equation 5 we can compute the probability, for a given distribution of $\sigma(c)$, of not finding any target after a complete search of A considering that it does not depend on the specific route of the seekers (this is clearly not true but it is assumed for simplicity) and that no seeker route overlaps with another:

$$P[\sigma] = \prod_{c \in \mathcal{D}(A)} \sum_{k=0}^{n_T} P_{\text{ND}|c}^{(k)}(c, \sigma) P^{(k)}(c) \quad (6)$$

To obtain the optimal search effort allocation, we need to solve the following optimization problem:

$$\text{minimize}_{\sigma} P[\sigma] \quad (7)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{c \in \mathcal{D}(A)} \sigma \Delta A = \Phi_T \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma \geq 0. \quad (9)$$

We could try to directly solve Equation 7 numerically, but we opted for another approach which yields goods results and can almost be solve by hand. We consider the functional

$$J[\sigma] = \Delta A \log P[\sigma] = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{D}(A)} \Delta A \log \sum_{k=0}^{n_T} P_{\text{ND}|c}^{(k)}(c, \sigma) P^{(k)}(c), \quad (10)$$

and then take the limit $\Delta A \rightarrow dA$ and $c \rightarrow \mathbf{x}$, which transforms the summation to the integral

$$J[\sigma] = \iint_A dA \log \sum_{k=0}^{n_T} P_{\text{ND}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}, \sigma) P^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (11)$$

Then, the problem can be solved using the Euler-Lagrange equations for an auxiliary variable $z^2 = \sigma$ using the Lagrangian

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \sigma) = \log \sum_{k=0}^{n_T} P_{\text{ND}|\mathbf{x}}^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}, \sigma) P^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}) + \lambda \sigma, \quad (12)$$

where λ is the Lagrange multiplier for the constraint Equation 8. This yields the following equation for σ and λ

$$\sigma \cdot \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n_T} (k - \lambda) P^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}) e^{-k\sigma} \right] = 0. \quad (13)$$

From a simple glimpse, we deduce that σ can either take the value 0 or satisfy the polynomial equation for $q = e^{-\sigma} \in (0, 1]$ within the brackets. The former can be solved easily using the any regular root finding algorithm for a given λ . This can be done iteratively by changing λ between 0 and n_T until the constraint Equation 8 is met. Then, the solution is known. This also includes the solution for the original problem and theory in [6].

III. MULTI-UAV PLANNING

Given the optimal search effort allocation for the mission as a density $\sigma : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ we now want to construct a plan that takes advantage of that information and also provides realistic routes for the UAS. This means that the local values of σ must somehow be translated into the path of each drone in the team, taking into account their physical limitations (minimum turning radius, limited autonomy, etc.) and collision avoidance both among the team members and with the terrain. This process is detailed in the following sections.

A. From optimal search effort allocation to priority subareas

First we define a set of priority subareas $\mathcal{S}(A)$ of A that can be built in the following manner:

- 1) Take a parameter $n \in \mathbb{N}$ chosen by the user. Then, compute $\phi = \Phi_T/n$.
- 2) Using the contour lines $\sigma = z$ (z is the parameter that selects different lines) we find the region R_1 with higher z that exactly contains $\phi = \sum_{c \in R_1} \sigma(c) \Delta A$ search effort within. This might generate several different disconnected areas. If this is the case, treat each area as independent and redo this step until all contain ϕ search effort.
- 3) Repeat the previous step for lower values of z and eliminating the overlap between the current region R_i and the previous one, i.e., $R_i = \{c \in \mathcal{D}(A) \mid z_i \leq \sigma \leq z_{i-1}; \sum_{c \in R_i} \sigma(c) \Delta A = \phi\}$. This is done recursively until the region not contained in any other region contains $\leq \phi$ search effort. Then, the last region is defined as the region between the previous one and the contour $\sigma = 0$. To each region R_i , we attach a priority value. In our case, we chose the total not finding probability within the region, that is

$$P_i = \prod_{c \in R_i} \sum_{k=0}^{n_T} P_{\text{ND}|c}^{(k)}(c, \sigma(c)) P^{(k)}(c). \quad (14)$$

The lower P_i , the higher the priority we assign to covering that area.

- 4) We might also define the region where $\sigma = 0$ as R_\emptyset .

At the end of the process, we end up with a set $\mathcal{S}(A)$ that fulfills $\bigcup_{R \in \mathcal{S}(A)} R = A/R_\emptyset$.

B. From priority subareas to coverage paths

The second step is to compute, for n_S seekers, the shortest possible paths between regions taking into account their respective priority levels in the order at which each of them is

visited. To do that, we use the Traveling Salesman Problem-based model developed in [18] using a custom graph and cost function.

Fig. 2: Traveling Salesman Problem-based graph that models the area visit tour problem for 5 priority subregions. In red, the representation of the seekers' base. In blue, each of the subareas. The values P_i contain the priority levels while d_{ij} contain the travel cost between nodes.

To construct the graph, we represent each subarea (except R_\emptyset) as a vertex and an additional one for the base of the drones (see Figure 2). Then, each priority level P_i is assigned to the corresponding vertex and the travel costs d_{uij} between all possible pairs are computed for each drone u using the energy model presented at [19] considering that the distance between areas is the minimum possible. The two points, one for area, at which this distance occurs are stored for later use. We refer to them as \mathbf{x}_i^s and \mathbf{x}_i^f for the entry and exit point of the subarea R_i respectively.

Then, we find a route for each drone that minimizes the cost function:

$$F(\{z, \theta\}) = \sum_{u=1}^{n_S} \left[\sum_{i,j \in \mathcal{S}(A)} d_{uij} z_{uij} - K \sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}(A)} \theta_{uk} P_k \right], \quad (15)$$

where $\{z\}$ are binary variables that select the actual route of each drone, $\{\theta\}$ are integer variables that encode the position within each route of each visited area and $K > 0$ is an arbitrary positive number to adjust the partial weight of each term in the total cost (for details, see [18]). The routes yielded by the algorithm visit all areas exactly once and by only one drone (to ensure no search overlap) and are cyclic in the base.

Once we know which subareas are visited by which drone and at what order we can compute the path plan within them. We compute the coverage path plan (CPP) for each subarea using \mathbf{x}_i^s and \mathbf{x}_i^f as the starting and end position. To do that we use a custom branch of the multi-drone CPP (mCPP) algorithm presented at [20] that enables the use of custom parameters. This mCPP algorithm computes an energy efficient plan to cover a polygon using parallel tracks.

Considering that the principal tracks are much longer than the turning legs of the path and that the movement speeds of the seekers v_s are constant, we can obtain a value for the sweeping width W_i (separation between tracks) used in each subarea (see Figure 3) based on their priority level.

Fig. 3: Visual representation of the sweeping width W and the detection range R_S

First, we compute the average $\langle\sigma\rangle_i$ for each area using $\langle\sigma\rangle_i = \frac{1}{\sum_{c \in R_i} \Delta A} \sum_{c \in R_i} \sigma(c) \Delta A$. As we are using parallel tracks, it is easy to see that $\gamma_s = \frac{R_S}{W \Delta t}$, where R_S is the detection range (as a diameter) of each drone's detector and Δt is the time required to inspect a cell. We can then assign to all cells within each subarea R_i the average value of the search effort density (to keep the same total within the area) so it is homogeneous at each region. We define the sweeping width for each one as $W_i = R_S / \langle\sigma\rangle_i$. This value is clipped to a certain range $[W_{\min}, W_{\max}]$ to avoid widths that are too small or large. Each W_i is then used to compute the CPP of the corresponding subarea. All plans yielded by the mCPP algorithm corresponding to a single drone are merged into a unique path. The travel to the base at the end and from the base at the start are also added.

C. Path Conflicts resolution

In this section, we consider potential collisions between drones and the terrain and between drones with other drones. Consider a mountainous region where very steep and narrow mountains might be present (see Figure 4a). If the distance between two waypoints is large enough, the straight line trajectory regularly considered might clip through the terrain and collision risks arise.

To fix this, we propose a simple yet efficient solution. The user defines a minimum and maximum height above the terrain h_{\min} and h_{\max} (see Figure 4b). If n_S drones are used, then the interval $[h_{\min}, h_{\max}]$ is divided into n_S different values (including the two bounds) are each of them is assigned to a drone. This height above the terrain is maintained through the entire mission. The only caveat is that $(h_{\max} - h_{\min}) / n_S$ should be large enough to securely separate the drones.

This however does not address collision between drones at take off and landing. The base of a drone with height h_1 might be in the path of another drone with height $h_2 < h_1$. If for some reason, the first drone's take off is delayed, collision might happen. As a simple although energy inefficient solution, the may plan include waiting time just after take off to halt the mission until all drones are ready to proceed. A similar approach is used for landing although waiting times might only be added if needed and per drone. More efficient solutions should be developed in future works.

D. From paths to trajectories

Usually, the transition between path and trajectory is not direct as drones may have limited maneuvering abilities due to their kinematic and dynamic model characteristics. Let us consider for instance fixed-wing aircrafts whose turning ability and climb rate are limited to a certain minimum radius and maximum gradient respectively. Using these two parameters, each path can be post-processed to change invalid parts to their Dubins' path [21] equivalent (see Figure 4c). Clearly, this may make the trajectories longer and to avoid underestimating battery usage, a certain security percentage must be reserved.

Another issue considered is battery life or autonomy. Using the parameter Φ_T defined in Section II we can indirectly limit the global usage of battery. A very rough estimation of the path length needed to cover an area of size A might be

$$L_A \approx \sqrt{A} + \frac{A}{W} \approx \sqrt{A} + \frac{A}{R_S} \langle\sigma\rangle_A \approx \sqrt{A} + \frac{\Phi_A}{R_S}, \quad (16)$$

which can be obtained by considering that the characteristic linear size of the area is \sqrt{A} and that $\langle\sigma\rangle_A = \Phi_A / A$ (for a search effort quantity Φ_A spent inside A). This means that approximately the total travelled length $L_T \propto \Phi_T$. If we also consider that the speed of the drones are constant and we ignore weather, the value L_T can be related to mission time and energy costs easily.

For control over the individual search effort available, a cost for the search effort of each priority area $\phi_i = \sum_{c \in R_i} \sigma(c) \Delta A$ can be stored into the corresponding vertices of the graph from Subsection III-B. By adding the constraints $\sum_{R_i \in \mathcal{S}(A)} y_{R_i|u} \phi_i \leq \phi_u^{(\max)}$ for the maximum search effort $\{\phi_u^{(\max)}\}$ available for each drone, we can impose individual limits. The new binary variables $y_{R_i|u}$ are true if and only if the drone u visits the subregion R_i .

We remark that this is a very rough approximation and it should not be used just by itself as a drone autonomy limiter and we also add further checks. As an example, after the CPPs are computed, a more accurate path length and energy cost can be estimated using Dubins' paths and the aforementioned energy model [19]. In addition and as a safe measure, if the autonomy of a drone is not enough to cover their entire assigned route, it can be cut short and the rest of the path can either be ignored until the next mission or manually assigned to another drone if possible.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS FOR DEPLOYMENT ON FIELD TESTS

To further validate the methods presented above, Software-In-The-Loop (SITL) simulations and real field tests will be carried out later in 2025. In order to do this, we connected the planner directly to the API of the autopilot of the Alpha A900 Helicopter UAV (see Figure 5). The A900 by Alpha Unmanned Systems¹ is an advanced helicopter UAV designed to meet a broad spectrum of operational needs, from intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance

¹<https://alphaunmannedsystems.com/>

Fig. 4: Solutions to three possible planning conflicts.

(ISR) tasks to detailed infrastructure assessments, border protection, and maritime monitoring. Built for challenging conditions, the A900 features duplicate systems for all mission-critical functions to safeguard against failure. Its propulsion comes from a two-stroke, low-vibration boxer engine, also powering an onboard generator that supplies up to 150W of power for payload usage. This design choice supports energy-demanding payloads without greatly diminishing flight duration. Whether operating in areas with or without GNSS signals, the vehicle relies on a radar altimeter and sophisticated navigation aids to maintain stability and accuracy. Moreover, its capacity for automated takeoffs and landings from moving platforms and design adherence to STANAG 4738 standards highlight its suitability for both civilian, academic and military use. Another important advantage is its portability and ease of deployment. Weighing less than 25 kilograms at take-off, the A900 requires minimal support infrastructure for transport and launch. Its four-hour flight capability and a cruising speed of 60 km/h allow it to adapt to rapidly changing mission parameters. In addition, compliance with rigorous standards—such as MIL-STD 416F and 810F for its autopilot, along with EN61000 and IP64 ratings for its servos—ensures that the vehicle meets stringent safety and performance benchmarks.

A standout characteristic of the A900 is its modular payload integration. With four distinct bays available, it can carry up to four kilograms of equipment, allowing operators to install a variety of sensors or communication systems such as 5G, satcom devices, EO/IR cameras, LiDAR systems, maritime AIS radars, or even IMSI capture devices for signal intelligence.

In particular, for our tests we plan to equip the A900 with the Lifeseeker Mini² developed by CENTUM Research & Technology, which is an advanced airborne system designed to enhance search and rescue (SAR) operations by transforming mobile phones into emergency beacons. This innovative payload is specifically tailored for integration with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), providing precise geolocation capabilities even in challenging environments. It embeds a proprietary algorithm to locate missing persons through their mobile phones with high precision, even in areas lacking network coverage and under adverse weather conditions. It operates across all network conditions, including 2G, 3G, 4G,

Fig. 5: The Alpha A900 is a multifunctional helicopter UAV for multi-purpose missions. Its design emphasizes durability, high payload capability, and prolonged flight time, making it a strong candidate for research and development environments where testing technology and ensuring system redundancy are critical.

and 5G, and remains effective even when no network signal is available. It can locate individuals without requiring any action from the missing person or collaboration from network service providers.

As it was mentioned above, in order to prepare the real flights, we will perform SITL tests with the algorithms implemented into a system which simulates the interaction between the UAV (including the physical movement), its API, the planner and the user (see Figure 6). The user creates an initial configuration file in JSON format that contains all the relevant information to fully define the problem (see JSON File 1).

Fig. 6: Structure and workflow of the implementation of the planner with the drones API and the user.

This file can be broken down into this items:

- **Area of Interest “aoi”:** It contains two set of latitude-longitude coordinates that defines a rectangle within Earth’s surface. Additionally, polygonal no-fly zones can be defined in a similar manner.

²<https://centum.com/en/products/lifeseeker/>

JSON File 1: Initialization file archetype

```

"aoi": {
  "lb": [lat, lon],
  "rt": [lat, lon],
  "no_fly_zones": {
    "nfz1": [
      [lat1, lon1],
      [lat2, lon2],
      [lat3, lon3], ... More points
    ], ... More No-Fly zones
  }
},
"pdfs": {
  "target1": {
    "center": [lat, lon],
    "great_ax": [dir_E, dir_N],
    "e": eccentricity
  }, ... More targets
},
"mission_parameters": {
  "max_height_ag" = value_m,
  "min_height_ag" = value_m,
  "max_SE" = value_m2,
  "uavs": {
    "uav1": {
      "avg_speed": value_mps,
      "base_pos": [lat, lon]
      "min_turn_radius": value_m,
      "max_gradient": value_max,
      "max_time": value_min,
    }, ... More UAVs
  }
}

```

- **Probability density function of the targets “pdfs”:** To simplify the input processing, we considered that most input probability density functions (PDFs) can be modeled using 2D Gaussian distributions. In this file, several PDFs can be defined by their centroid using Latitude-Longitude coordinates, its major deviation (including direction and value in meters) and the eccentricity of the distribution.
- **Miscellaneous mission parameters “mission_parameters”:** These are parameters that define the rest of the problem including the maximum available search effort and the details of the drones used.

The initialization JSON file can be given to the planner solver as either a local *.json* file or using a POST request into the corresponding API. After that, the planner computes the optimal search effort allocation as explained in Section II and then the individual trajectories as in Section III. The final plan is then sent to each of the UAVs’ APIs (or autopilot’s) via another POST/PUT request.

After this, usually the user checks if the mission is valid and either rejects or starts it. If started, a communication loop is activated between the planner (sending updates of the initial plan) and the swarm of drones (sending back information about their status: GNSS location, battery level and speed) to actively check for conflicts and dynamically solve them if needed using the methods explained in Subsection III-C. This kind of loops allow the relaxation of the constraints of the initial planning as solving issues mid-flight is possible and sometimes more efficient although more risky. If the planner detects that something might go wrong, a new plan can be automatically computed and sent to the drones via their respective APIs.

Another important aspect is the constant updates done

to the victims’ probability density functions due to the new information gathered. This can be done using Bayes’ theorem. The new probability density functions can be easily computed as the finding probabilities of individual victims are independent. After a certain amount of mission time, these updates can be used to obtain updated plans for the remaining of the mission.

V. VALIDATION RESULTS

Let us consider the problem shown in Figure 7. The selected region is roughly $13.8 \approx 104 \text{ km}^2$ and located at the south of Spain, in Almuñecar. Such size have been chosen to stress test the planner and in real life scenarios, much smaller areas will be actually considered so they can be covered with real UAVs. Five different probability density functions (Figure 7a) were randomly generated using Gaussian distributions, generated by picking a random location and bell width from two different uniform distributions adjusted to the region size. The probability of at least one target being at each cell is also shown in Figure 7b. The region was discretized into $50 \cdot 50$ cells and the problem was solved using the aforementioned methods taking around 20 s on average for the entire process running in a single thread of a AMD R5 5600X using Python 3.12 and NumPy. The solution for the optimal search effort allocation with $\Phi_T = 16 \text{ km}^2$ ($\sim 15\%$ of the actual area) with a probability $1 - P \approx 0.67$ of finding at least one target after a complete mission is shown in Figure 7c. Also, the priority subregions generated for $n = 3$ are displayed.

As the total search effort given is not enough to cover the entire area, some regions of A are not even covered ($\sigma = 0$). It is better to spend more search effort into regions where a target is more likely to be in than trying to cover the entire area. This result is very well known in search theory [6], [11]. Also, as the search effort density is higher in higher priority zones, the corresponding subregion is smaller in size so the total search effort is equal in all the subregions.

Although the total search effort is $\Phi_T = 16 \text{ km}^2$, the area of the two larger subregions are 20 km^2 . This is due to the fact that the total search effort is related to the effective area scanned, taking into account overlaps and that the same patch of surface can be only partially search if the search effort density is lower than unity.

In Figure 7d and Figure 7e, the routes for $n_S = 5$ seekers are shown. All of them have the same sensor with a detection range $R_S = 100 \text{ m}$. The sweeping width has been limited between $0.1R_S$ and $10R_S$. As expected, the higher priority regions are visited first and with more dense parallel tracks. As lower priority zones are scanned, the sweeping width gets progressively wider.

As a another test, in Figure 7f we plotted the elevation profile of each seeker along the length of their corresponding path including the total length. Many of the seekers stay in the flat and hence, their elevation is approximately constant. On the other hand, the orange seeker, goes into the mountainous region of the area and follows the terrain accordingly. Another remark is that as we are not limiting the individual

Fig. 7: A region of space roughly 104 km^2 discretized into $50 \cdot 50$ cells. 5 targets are randomly scattered in the region and a randomly generated circular Gaussian distribution is used for the probability density function of the position of each of them. The contour lines represent the elevation map of the region. The generated paths correctly cover the area from high priority to low priority areas taking into account the safety elevation difference over the terrain and between each UAV while distributing the work as much as possible with the current method. The difference between path lengths could be improved by using more priority zones instead of just 5.

Fig. 8: Dependency of the total path length L_T and the finding probability $1 - P[\sigma]$ on several input parameters: the total search effort Φ_T , the number of seekers (UAS) n_S and the number of targets n_T . Each point is computed as the average of 10 runs using the indicate parameter values. The linear approximation overestimates real path length. The finding probability increases with the effort used an the number of targets as expected.

search effort, the total length of the paths may differ between each other. In the given example, the shortest route is 3/5 of the longest. The distribution of path length could also be improved by simply using more priority zones. As each of them is only visited by a single UAV, using more of them adds flexibility so a better distribution could be found. This however makes the computation time longer.

In Figure 8a, we plotted the total path length (as a sum of all path lengths) as a function of Φ_T . Each point is the average of 10 random runs in the region and conditions as previously defined. We can see that although the linear approximation Equation 16 is a pretty good approximation for lower values of Φ_T it is violated when increased. As we anticipated, this is just a rough approximation. We however can use it a higher bound for total path length as the actual values obtained in the simulation always stays under it. The proportionality constant $1/R_S$ diverges from the ideal $1/100 \text{ m}^{-1}$ to approximately $1/125 \text{ m}^{-1}$. Another important characteristic is that the curves obtained are independent on the number of seekers used in the mission.

As a final test, in Figure 8b we plotted the probability of finding at least one target $1 - P[\sigma]$ in the same manner. As expected, as Φ_T and the number of targets n_T get higher, so does the probability.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a new planning method for a swarm of UAVs in search and rescue operations is presented and successfully validated numerically. A new probabilistic formulation to obtain the optimal search effort allocation compatible with multi-seeker multi-target scenarios was defined. A Traveling Salesman Problem solver was successfully applied to compute the optimal sub-area visiting order distribution and an energy-aware path planner was used to compute the corresponding UAVs coverage path plans. A method to merge and postprocess these paths into trajectories, including rules for the resolution of collision and battery constraints, was also presented.

The approach was validated numerically by performing hundreds of randomized simulations. The mathematical models obtained good results for the probability of finding targets and the planner achieves promising results that need to be further validated by performing real field tests.

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